

Wellcome Trust	Information
Data management plan required?	Yes
RDM policy Link	https://wellcome.ac.uk/funding/managing-grant/policy-data-software-materials-management-and-sharing
Definition of data	Datasets generated by research, original software, new materials generated (antibodies, cell lines, reagents) - this is particular for output management.
Length of data management plan	700 words
DMP template/ requirements	https://wellcome.ac.uk/funding/managing-grant/developing-outputs-management-plan
Required data repository	Should be a recognised community repository
Time for data release	At time of publication at a minimum, or where public health emergencies are involved in advance of journal publication.
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	<p>Can apply for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One or more dedicated data manager or data scientist (full/ part-time) Data and software management training for research or support staff DO Not consider costs for occasional or routine support from institutional managers or other support staff. Dedicated hardware or software required to deliver research Accessing a supercomputer or other shared facilities Operation of an access committee or other data access mechanism Costs of preparing and sharing data, software or materials with users Costs of ingesting secondary data, code or materials from users Costs associated with accessing data, software or materials from other researchers Deposition and preservation of data, software and materials Ingestion or deposition costs to recognised subject repositories for data, code and materials Data or code deposition in unstructured repositories where no recognised subject repository exists Where there is no suitable repository, ingestion costs for institutional repositories may be considered DO NOT consider estimated costs for curation and maintenance of data, code and materials beyond the lifetime of the award (willing to discuss very high-value outputs)

	Costs associated with routine data storage should be met by the institution unless requirements exceed institutional capacity.
Last updated	June 2017
Contact Details	d.carr@wellcome.ac.uk
Comments	N/A

Documents used:

Wellcome Trust's Policy on data, software and materials management and sharing
<https://wellcome.ac.uk/funding/guidance/policy-data-software-materials-management-and-sharing>

Wellcome Trust's outputs management plan <https://wellcome.ac.uk/funding/managing-grant/developing-outputs-management-plan>

Accessed: May 2018